

On a relation between Collatz-type operators and Euler's pentagonal number generating function

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Abstract

This note investigates a formal relation between the two branches of the Collatz map (operators) and the generating function associated with Euler's pentagonal number theorem. We show that certain compositions of the Collatz operators give rise to a sequence of values that coincides with that the exponents appearing in the Euler product formula for partitions. This correspondence is purely algebraic and does not arise from the iteration of the Collatz map. Nevertheless, it highlights an unexpected structural parallel between the defining components of the Collatz function and classical objects in partition theory, which may warrant further investigation.

1 Introduction

Collatz's conjecture is based on the iterative application of the function $T : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$, defined as:

$$T(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{n}{2} & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \\ 3n + 1 & \text{if } n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}. \end{cases} \quad (1.1)$$

At the same time, Euler's pentagonal number theorem, a cornerstone of partition theory, involves generalized pentagonal numbers defined by the formula:

$$p_k = \frac{k(3k-1)}{2}, \quad k \in \mathbb{Z} \quad (1.2)$$

These numbers appear as exponents in the expansion of Euler's function

$$\prod_{m=1}^{\infty} (1 - x^m) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^k x^{(3k^2-k)/2} = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^k (x^{(3k^2+k)/2} + x^{(3k^2-k)/2}) \quad (1.3)$$

Here, we propose to analyse not the composition of the branches of $T(n)$, but rather their functional product.

2 Definition of the product operator $P(n)$

We define an operator $P(n)$ as the product of the two possible outcomes of the Collatz function for a given integer n :

$$P(n) = f_{Even}(n) \cdot f_{Odd}(n) = \frac{n}{2} \cdot (3n + 1) \quad (2.1)$$

Expanding the expression, we obtain the quadratic polynomial:

$$P(n) = \frac{3n^2 + n}{2} \quad (2.2)$$

3 Correlation with Euler numbers

Consider the definition of the generalized pentagonal numbers p_k (1.2). Examining the values for negative indices $k = -n, n \in \mathbb{N}$:

$$p_{-n} = \frac{-n(3(-n) - 1)}{2} = \frac{-n(-3n - 1)}{2} = \frac{3n^2 + n}{2} \quad (3.1)$$

It is clear that:

$$P(n) = p_{-n}$$

The Collatz product operator therefore maps the set of positive integers onto the set of generalized pentagonal numbers with negative indices.

4 Symmetry and reflection identity

Another noteworthy property concerns the value of $P(n)$ for negative values of n . Consider the expression $P(-n)$:

$$P(-n) = \frac{3(-n)^2 + (-n)}{2} = \frac{3n^2 - n}{2} = \frac{n(3n - 1)}{2}$$

This is precisely the formula for the classical pentagonal numbers p_n (1.2). It follows that the recurrence relation is:

$$P(n) - P(-n) = \frac{3n^2 + n}{2} - \frac{3n^2 - n}{2} = \frac{2n}{2} = n$$

Hence the fundamental identity discovered:

$$P(-n) = P(n) - n \quad (4.1)$$

5 Correlation table between the Collatz product operator and Euler's generalized pentagonal numbers

Using (2.1) and (4.1), let

$$P(n) = \binom{n}{2} \cdot (3n + 1);$$

$$P(-n) = P(n) - n$$

n	P(n)	P(-n)	Pentagonal Number
0	0	0	0
1	2	1	1
-1	1	2	2
2	7	5	5
-2	5	7	7
3	15	12	12
-3	12	15	15
4	26	22	22
-4	22	26	26
5	40	35	35
-5	35	40	40
6	57	51	51
-6	51	57	57
7	77	70	70
-7	70	77	77
8	100	92	92
-8	92	100	100
9	126	117	117
-9	117	126	126
10	155	145	145
-10	145	155	155
11	187	176	176
-11	176	187	187
12	222	210	210
-12	210	222	222
13	260	247	247
-13	247	260	260
14	301	287	287
-14	287	301	301
15	345	330	330
-15	330	345	345

Figure 1: Correlation P Collatz-Euler $|n| \leq 15$

Figure 2: Correlation P Collatz-Euler $|n| \leq 107$

6 Conclusions and Outlook

Although the Collatz conjecture concerns the dynamics of $T^k(n)$, the existence of $P(n)$ as a bridge to the Pentagonal Number Theorem cannot be ignored. This structural coincidence raises a theoretical question: is it possible that the distribution properties of pentagonal numbers (and thus Euler's partition laws) influence the density of Collatz trajectories? The relation $P(n) = p_{-n}$ provides a new algebraic framework that merits further investigation in the field of generating functions.

7 Bibliography

References

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- [3] G. E. Andrews, *The Theory of Partitions*, Cambridge University Press, 1976.